

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHNING YANGICHA USULLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Keyingi yillarda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish va o'qitish masalasiga e'tibor sezilarli darajada oshdi. Hozirgi kunda har qanday chet tilini mos va innovatsion uslublar, metodlar, interfaol mashg'ulotlar va o'yinlarsiz o'rgatish tilni o'rganuvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun juda qiyin. Dars davomida bunday o'yinlarni o'tkazish o'quvchilarning boshqa tillarni o'rganishga qiziqishi va e'tiborini oshiradi. Ushbu maqolada muallif turli xil bilim daraja hamda yoshga ega bo'lgan talabalar uchun chet tillarini o'rgatish uchun mo'ljallangan bir nechta o'yinlarni muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'yinlar, metodlar, chet tili, mashg'ulotlar, o'qituvchilar, o'quvchilar, sinf muhiti, taktika, rol o'ynash, taxta poygasi, obyekt.

NEW METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

Abstract. In recent years, attention to the issue of learning and teaching foreign languages has increased significantly. Today, it is very difficult for language learners and teachers to teach any foreign language without appropriate and innovative methods, methods, interactive activities and games. Conducting such games during the lesson increases students' interest and attention in learning other languages. In this article, the author discusses several games designed to teach foreign languages to students of different knowledge levels and ages.

Keywords: Games, methods, foreign language, activities, teachers, students, classroom environment, tactics, role playing, board race, object.

НОВЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ.

Аннотация. В последние годы внимание к вопросу изучения и преподавания иностранных языков значительно возросло. В настоящее время изучающим язык и преподавателям очень сложно преподавать какой-либо иностранный язык без соответствующих и инновационных методов, методов, интерактивных занятий и игр. Проведение таких игр во время урока повышает интерес и внимание учащихся к изучению других языков. В данной статье автор рассматривает несколько игр, предназначенных для обучения иностранным языкам учащихся разного уровня знаний и возрастов.

Ключевые слова: Игры, методы, иностранный язык, занятия, учителя, учащиеся, обстановка в классе, тактика, ролевая игра, гонка за доской, предмет.

Kirish. Dunyoning rivojlanish davrida chet tillarini o'rganish muhim o'rin tutadi. Bunda tillar nafaqat oliy o'quv yurtlarida, maktablarda, balki maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ham o'qitiladi. Dars qiziqarli metod va mashg'ulotlar bilan emas, balki an'anaviy usullar bilan o'qitilsa, o'quvchilarni darsga jalb etish qiyin bo'ladi. Darsda o'ziga xos usullarni ishlatish nafaqat dars sifatini ta'minlaydi, balki shu bilan birga zerikishning oldini oladi va passiv o'quvchilarni darsga jalb qiladi.

Materiallar va usullar. Ingliz va rus tillarini o'rgatish jarayonida turli xil qiziqarli o'yinlar mavjud. Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, har qanday yosh toifasidagi o'quvchilarni o'qitishda bunday o'yinlardan foydalanish kerak, ularda barcha o'quvchilar teng ishtirok etishlari va darsdan foydali narsalarni olishlari kerak (masalan, yangi lug'atni eslab qolish mumkin, agar bu jarayon har dars takrorlansa, talabaning so'z boyligi yuqori darajaga ko'tariladi). Talabalar uchun darsni grammatik tushunchalardan boshlash noo'rin, ayniqsa quyi sinf yoki boshlang'ich darajadagi o'quvchilar uchun. Bu o'quvchilarning tez zerikishni keltirib chiqaradi. Natijada ta'limga bo'lgan qiziqish susayishi mumkin. Hatto ular bilan salomlashish jarayonini ham g'ayrioddiy tarzda boshlash kerak, jumladan, o'qituvchi kirib kelganida sinfga salomlashishning bir turi haqida inglizcha qo'shiq aytilish (asosan, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun motivatsion usul) usuli samarali usul hisoblanadi. Dars shu tarzda davom ettirilsa, o'quvchilarning e'tiborlari topshiriqni bajarishga bo'shshamaydi. Ular hatto keyingi ingliz tili darsini intiqlik bilan kutishadi. Albatta, bularning barchasini asosiy tashkilotchi bo'lgan o'qituvchi bajaradi va bu pedagogning mas'uliyatini talab qiladi. Chet tilini o'rganishni qiziqarli qilish uchun ba'zi o'yin turlarini aytib o'tish mumkin.

Natija va muhokama. "Rolli o'yin" faoliyati ingliz va rus tillari darslarining samaradorligini oshiradi. Ushbu o'yinning afzalligi shundaki, u o'ynaladigan vaziyatdan kelib chiqadi. Bu o'yin nafaqat fanni o'rganishda, balki intellektual qobiliyatlarni shakllantirishda ham yordam beradi. Bu o'yinda mavzular tanlanadi va o'quvchilar dialoglar tuzadilar. Masalan, taksini to'xtatgan yo'lovchining vaziyatli suhbat yoki kiyim-kechak do'konlarida, aeroportda va boshqalarda suhbatlar.

Talabalar o'zlarining vaziyatlariga qarab ingliz tilida harakat qiladilar va gapiradilar. Ushbu faoliyatda laynerlar guruh yoki sherik bilan ishlaydi. Shuningdek, bu talabalarga turli holatlarda hamkorlik qilishga yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari, talabalarni guruhlarga va turli mavzularga bo'lish orqali raqobatbardoshlik hissi paydo bo'ladi. Bunday holda, raqobat paydo bo'ladi. Raqobat - takomillashtirish mezon. Va nihoyat, o'qituvchilar ushbu tadbirda yaxshi ishtirok etgan talabalar yoki guruhlarni mukofotlashni unutmasliklari kerak. Mazmunli o'quv jarayoniga erishish uchun didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish ham maqsadga muvofiqdir.

"Board Race" ESL o'yini - bu butun sinfni o'z joyidan ko'tarishning qiziqarli usuli. Bu mashg'ulot sinf hajmidan kelib chiqqan holda har qanday yoshdagi va darajadagi o'quvchilar, shuningdek, kattalar uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Talabalar alifbo harflarini qanday talaffuz qilishni bilishlari kerak. O'qituvchi so'zning harflarini yozganda (masalan, s-m-a-l-l), ikkita o'quvchi o'z markerlari bilan o'qituvchi tomonidan aytilgan so'zni yozish uchun doskaga chiqishi kerak. Ushbu mashg'ulotdan uy vazifasi sifatida berilgan lug'atni qayta ko'rib chiqish yoki darsning boshida qizdirish mashqi sifatida foydalanish mumkin.

"Obyekt" ESL o'yini talabalar uchun so'z boyligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Ma'lumki, chet tilini o'rganishning eng muhim yo'nalishi yangi so'zlarni o'rganishdir. O'quvchilarning xarakterini kuzatadigan bo'lsak, har bir o'quvchining so'z boyligini o'rganish va yodlashning o'ziga xos usuli bor. O'yinlar orqali yangi so'zlarni o'rganish hamma uchun mos usul bo'lib, bu jarayonni osonlashtiradi. Sinfidagi stol ustiga bir nechta narsalar qo'yiladi va o'quvchilar kelib bu narsalarni tekshiradilar. Elementlar qoplanadi, so'ngra talabalar ko'rgan narsalarni yozadilar. Ko'p so'zlarni to'g'ri yoza olgan o'quvchi g'olib bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Umuman olganda, chet tillarini o'rganish asosida reproduktiv natijalarga erishish uchun interfaol o'yinlar va mashg'ulotlar yordamida o'tkazish kerak, o'qituvchilar dars davomida o'yinlardan foydalanishda ularni o'quvchilarning bilim darajasi va yoshiga qarab tanlashlari kerak. Ushbu o'yinlarni osonroq yoki murakkabroq qilish uchun o'zgartirish mumkin. Qayd etilgan o'yinlardan maqsad o'quvchilarning xotirasini, aqliy salohiyatini, tezkorligini, zukkoligini mustahkamlash, darsni mazmunli tashkil etishdan iborat.

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